

RESPONSE PAPER

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PROGRAM CODE: MDIA

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PERIOD NUMBER: 1

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Edit or delete text to show actual information below:The author applied UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (in-text/parenthetical)

The author did did *not* use Zotero to insert referencesThe author did did *not* use Grammarly Premium (EUCLID provides access)

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 8)

List your 7 key concepts with page number in text (then bold these terms in your RP)(samples below):

1. Knowledge and Evidence-based (EUCLID 2019, 24-26)
2. Purpose Driven (EUCLID 2019, 17-19)
3. Detailed Oriented (EUCLID 2019, 28)
4. Disillusionment (EUCLID 2019, 47-51)
5. Sanction (EUCLID 2019, 16)
6. Accuracy Driven (EUCLID 2019, 41)
7. Clarity of Purpose (EUCLID 2019)

ACA-401/ACA-401 COURSEPACK

1) INTRODUCTION

The Authors, Prof. Laurent Cleenewerck and Dr. Kabiru Gulma, of ACA-401/ACA-401D, Period 1; Revised Edition, published in Bangui, Central Africa Republic: Euclid University; 2019, is primarily for the purpose of broadening the knowledge and enhancing the skills of Students and Readers amidst their quest to write an excellent piece of academic and professional paper.

This piece of work is detailed oriented, espouses the step-by-step guide that is required of a very good material, reader friendly, very comprehensive, and extensively dealt with the contemporary realities of writing a very good academic Material. Against this background, I am personally convinced that it meets the needs and standards of an excellent academic and professional writing purposes.

In view of the above introduction, I write to personally subscribe to the fact that this piece of work; by every indication, meets its course objective and at best, recommended for its intended purposes.

2) OVERVIEW OF THE COURSEPACK

A detailed reading, utmost comprehension, and strict adherence to ACA-401/ACA-401D for Period 1, Revised by Prof. Laurent Cleenewerck and Dr. Kabiru Gulma, in no uncertain terms will improve and standardize one's reading ability and research methodology which are vital to writing a very good academic and professional piece of work. It is a truism that stands the test of time that graduate programs are embedded with a lot of writing and research, for example, one must do five response papers, one quiz and one major paper per course. Be it as it may, this requires a lot of reading and writing. As a result, this book is **purpose driven**, timely and relevant to prepare you for the multiple tasks ahead

In my view, the above assertion pretty much holds true against the backdrop that, the piece of work under review makes it clear that; "reading and researching are vital to essay writing" (EUCLID 2019, 2). Literally, to write an essay or response paper on any piece of work, one requires an in-depth knowledge on that piece of work he or she is writing on. In that regard, he or she must read and research a lot on that topic. The more the required information you acquire, the better you are inclined and knowledgeable to write an excellent essay, "Research provides the **knowledge and evidence** that allows you to develop a thesis and argument to answer the essay question" (ibid.).

3) OBJECTIVES OF THE COURSEPACK

As referenced above, ACA-401/ACA-401D coursepack for period one meets its required standards and fulfills its course objectives. In other words, the information entails in this coursepack are exceptional and can be used at any level in academia. It touches the rudiment and gives in-depth analysis of a writing process. As a result, it is reader friendly, guides you through the basic and fundamental principles of writing. This, however, serves as a solid foundation for teaching and learning purposes. This further defines exactly what the students should be able to know and do by the end of the course. Indeed, and without doubt, when the course objective are clearly communicated to the students, it is more than likely that they will achieve their desired goals. The main objective of ACA-104/ACA-401D is to prepare the reader/student with the skills, relevant information and dynamics that are involved in writing a piece of academic work. Consequent upon the adequate information that are embedded in the material under review, one will say it is quite an exceptional academic piece of work.

4) AMERICAN VERSUS BRITISH ENGLISH

Moreover. As a native of a British colonized of a West African state, with a long standing British academic values and orientation, I was hitherto very cynical about the American English and spellings in many fronts. For instance, 'if I was you' [American] as against 'if I were you' [British]. Another example is the spelling of 'cheque' [British] as

against ‘check’ [American], colour [British] and color [American], to name but a few. With this variation in mind, I thought the American English was distorted and unstandardized until I went through ACA-401/ACA-401D. This piece of excellent academic work got me **disillusioned** and invariably reconciled me with the variation. Now, I have an understanding and a clear-cut conviction that, the American English is not as distorted as I thought and that, ACA-401 coursepack further educated me with the fact that,” American English is currently the dominant influence on world English” (EUCLID 2019, 28). The significance of knowing this is that it gives you a consistency flow in your writing scheme. In other words, if you are using American English, you should as well use the American spelling, dictions, punctuations etc. as well as the British English, except for the purpose of clarification. “IT IS GOOD TO KNOW WHAT WORDS AND EXPRESSIONS ARE UNIQUELY BRITISH VS AMERICAN” (EUCLID 2019, 41), which characterizes the features of a standard academic and professional writing attribute.

5) HOW TO USE A RESPONSE PAPER TEMPLATE

The Video is a quite a laudable study guide that provides physical reality, in-depth analysis, and clear insight as to how a good response paper should look like. In my view, the video is primarily intended to facilitate teaching process and cognitive development, it is very important, in the scene that, it gives you the leverage and ample time to listen to the content of the presentation attentively, pause, rewind, and continue to be listening to your utmost understanding and satisfaction. The essence of this is for **clarity of purpose**. In this regard, I write to subscribe to the above assumption that the continuous viewing and listening to the video will invariably give one a deeper and clearer understanding of writing a better academic and professional paper. Consequently, the in-depth analysis, clarity of presentation and accuracy of its intended purpose, makes it worthy of emulation.

6) PLAGIARISM

Another thematic point that ACA-401 coursepack covers comprehensively is what I personally call academic theft (plagiarism). “Plagiarism is when the writer uses a source of information without giving credit to the author of the source of information” (EUCLID 2019, 27). In view of above, I write to personally submit that plagiarism is a crime and bears a severe consequence such as loss of credibility and professional standing. Also, “**sanctions** for plagiarism depend on its severity and may range from lower grade on an assignment to a failing grade for the course” (EUCLID 2019, 16). With this in mind; one is well guided in the mist of his or her research not to copy and paste someone’s information, neither using a writer’s information or quotation without giving him credit.

7) CURRICULUM VITAE

The author in preparing a prospective employee for employment, discusses the means of seeking and obtaining job, which I believe is very central for human existence in

contemporary world. Jobs can be sought and obtained by the quality of your curriculum vitae. “Curriculum vitae is a marketing tool advertising skills, abilities and educational credentials of a job hunter” (EUCLID 2019, 37). This document gives a detailed account of your personal information that a prospective employer might be interested in, and how it can be prepared. I realized that the author was using curriculum vitae and resume alternatively. In my opinion, he did this because he knows that these words are specifically used relative to your educational background. For instance, the word curriculum vitae is not commonly used in America, it is predominantly used in the UK and countries with related background. This as well holds true for resume. In essence, the author did this for the clarity of purpose and for the understanding of the reader.

To my understanding, he clearly underpinned the fact that curriculum vitae itself cannot hand you the job, however, a quality one will captivate the employer to select you for an interview. “from large numbers of responses, the employer typically selects for interview the curriculum vitae whom he believes will offer best talent” (EUCLID 2019, 41). This is a plausible information in establishing the mindset of the reader in preparing one, and that, the job hunter needs to have a thorough knowledge on the job adverts so that he/she will know the quality of employee the employer is looking for and designs his or her curriculum vitae in that respect. This information by every extent serves as a very good resource material. However, my personal inference from this sentence is that curriculum vitae is not a static document, in the science that, it should always be prepared relative to the information you are getting from the adverts. Nonetheless, even if a job hunter produces a very good curriculum vitae and could not succeed in the interview, he or she is unlikely to get the job. In essence, a good curriculum vitae, a letter of application, indicating the specific position you are applying for and a good impression in the interview will surely get you the job.

8) CONCLUSION

Owing to the course objective of ACA-401/ACA-401D, it is my opinion that it serves its purpose and meets the standards of an exceptional academic and professional piece of work. The material is reader friendly, compounded with relevant and detailed information and very comprehensive, which are the basis of a good work. In so far as the material is for academic purposes; it guides you with the styles and formats the use of relevant software and appropriate use of response paper templates that are required in an academic and professional arena. In view of this, I personally recommend it for professional writing and research-oriented purposes.

REFERENCES

Cleenerwerck Laurent and Kabiru Gulma, 2nd ed. 2019. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. Bangui, Central Africa Republic: Euclid University.

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